

The Role of Language-in-Education Policies in the Pursuit of Inclusive Quality Education in Seychelles

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Introduction

The UN Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4)¹ aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. The emphasis lies on improving access to education, enhancing learning outcomes, reducing disparities, and ensuring that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development. Efforts include language-sensitive and culturally relevant approaches. In Seychelles, these aims are clearly mirrored in the stated ambitions of the Ministry of Education (2024).

Mission: The Ministry of Education in Seychelles aims to build a comprehensive, quality education system that reflects shared values, promotes holistic development, and empowers citizens to participate fully in social and economic development.

Vision statement: To empower future citizens to contribute positively to the process of building a sustainable, peaceful and harmonious Seychelles society, whilst safeguarding and promoting our unique traditions and cultural values.²

Much research shows that policies related to the language of learning and instruction are key factors in ensuring quality education. Put more simply, learners perform best when taught in a language they have fully mastered. Despite of this, around 80% of children in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) are taught in ex-colonial second languages (L2) that they do not fully understand (The World Bank, 2021). Seychelles is no exception. In these contexts, *subtractive bilingual* systems, where instruction shifts abruptly to a second-language-only model in the early primary years, remain the norm, and transitions to second language medium of instruction (L2 MoI) often lack support and scaffolding, negatively impacting learning (Milligan et al., 2020; The World Bank, 2021).

Despite Seychelles' official trilingual policy, with Kreol Seselwa, English and French holding equal legal status, the reality on the ground reveals persistent educational challenges that may, in part, stem from unresolved language tensions. National

¹ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal4>

² <https://edu.gov.sc/mission-and-vision/>

examination results and student disengagement suggest that the current system may not be serving all learners effectively, and much research indicates that the limited role of Kreol Seselwa in formal education – particularly beyond the early primary years – may be part of the problem (Zelime 2022; Deutschmann and Zelime, 2022).

In this article, we will present evidence and arguments that illustrate how language-in-education aspects are central to many of the challenges facing education in Seychelles today. These challenges cannot be fully addressed without confronting the mismatch between the language of instruction and the language skills of the learners and teachers. Below we will address challenges at three different levels in the system: at the formal policy level; in the field, looking at aspects such as pedagogy and examination; and finally on a more general level, looking at aspects such as the role of language in identity construction and nation building. At the end of each section, we will present policy suggestions to address the challenges discussed. The article closes with a general summary and a vision statement.

Formal language-in-education policies – intentions and practice

Firstly, it is important to point out that language-in-education policies are only one of several components contributing to quality education (Trudell, 2016). Aspects such as infrastructure, teacher competency and pedagogy are also crucial in ensuring learner engagement. We would, however, argue that the language of instruction is a key ingredient in some of these aspects too. For example, as a teacher, it is challenging to reach your full professional competence potential in a language that you do not feel totally comfortable with. Furthermore, teaching and learning in a second requires special pedagogic solutions, especially in heterogenous learner groups with varied language competencies.

Findings from our own research (Zelime and Deutschmann, 2016) indicate that the expressed ambitions in the overarching policy documents, to work towards SDG4 and inclusive education in Seychelles, are high. The Seychelles National Curriculum Framework (NCF) is firmly anchored in both international human rights conventions and national legal commitments to promote equity, lifelong learning, and educational inclusivity. The framework underscores education as a fundamental right, highlighting compulsory ten-year schooling for all learners, irrespective of background, and emphasizes learner-centred, individualized instruction tailored to diverse needs and learning styles. The NCF aims to develop lifelong learners who are empowered to contribute meaningfully to both local and global communities. The NCF promotes continuity and adaptability in education to meet 21st-century challenges. Importantly, it links education to national development and community engagement, portraying learning as a collaborative, purposeful, and empowering process.

The Seychelles NCF also gives significant attention to language issues, recognizing language as central to learning and identity formation. It positions Kreol Seselwa prominently within the system. Kreol Seselwa is affirmed as the national first language and the main medium of instruction in early education, underlining its importance for self-expression and personal development. However, its role is framed largely as transitional, supporting the eventual acquisition of English and French.

The language challenges involved in using English as the medium of instruction from Primary 3 are understated in the NCF. For example, there is a general lack of acknowledgement of the subject-specific language requirements needed to learn other subjects through English. At secondary levels, when subjects are taught by different teachers, there is no systematic structure in place for communication and collaboration between language teachers and subject teachers so that students' potential language problems can be identified and dealt with (see Deutschmann and Zelime, 2014).

Despite the strong emphasis on equity and human rights, the NCF provides limited or no guidance on how to support learners struggling with English as a second language, as regards both instruction and assessment. There are no frameworks or resources in place for language support in the classroom and in assessment. In summary, language challenges are acknowledged, but insufficiently addressed in terms of practical implementation, highlighting a gap between stated principles and actionable strategies in the classroom.

This gap becomes obvious when looking at more specific policy aspects related to the English curriculum in particular. Based on national exam reports and subject curriculum content, Zelime (2022, p.20.) concludes that the main approach in the English curriculum is structural rather than communicative; in other words, that emphasis lies 'on how to write 'correct English', rather than on the language knowledge that the pupils need in order to learn through English'. There is thus no specific acknowledgement of the various subject-specific language requirements that English classes should prepare the learners for.

With reference to policies regarding language of support, official reports from the Ministry of Education seem to indicate that the use of Kreol Seselwa is actively discouraged in the field (Zelime and Deutschmann, 2016). The policy change of 2017 (see <https://www.nation.sc/archive/252671/cabinet-decisions>), providing for the use of English as MoI from Primary 1 in the subject of Mathematics, also shows how Kreol Seselwa is disfavoured in the education system.

In summary, there is a large gap between the intentions expressed in the NCF and praxis in the field. This, however, seems to be the norm in most SSA contexts; Trudell (2016, p.viii), for example, points out that over 90% of the countries studied in their report on language policies and practice in Africa support the use of local languages in education, but classroom practices rarely reflect these ambitions.

Policy suggestions

While it is recommendable that the NCF acknowledges the importance of language/s in the learning process, this general acknowledgement needs to be backed up by explicit praxis frameworks to realize the intentions of epistemic equity and inclusiveness. Based on the above, we recommend that the following aspects be given special attention in future language-in-education policy discussions and revisions.

1. Given that English is the medium of learning, the English curriculum should be adapted accordingly. Focus needs to be placed on communicative aspects of language learning, and there needs to be a careful alignment of the English curriculum with the language requirements of the various subjects at the different levels. This includes subject-specific vocabulary, but, more importantly, the ability to recognize and apply different academic genres and registers. One way forward may be to make space for language support slots in the timetable – English support classes, where one could focus on specific language challenges learners encounter in the different subjects.
2. In secondary schools, there should be a formal system in place for communication between English teachers and subject teachers. Regular meetings focussed on medium-of-instruction issues would give English teachers better insights into the needs of various subjects and also afford language support for subject teachers on how they can communicate in ways that are more accessible to learners with limited English proficiency. This is especially important for expatriate teachers (42% of the secondary teacher workforce in 2023 – see Ministry of Education, 2024), who do not speak Kreol Seselwa.
3. There is a need for: a) tools to identify learners who have difficulties understanding and expressing themselves in English; and b) systematic resources assigned to support these learners, in the form of teacher assistants and/or extra teaching, for example. Furthermore, we would argue for a legal framework that recognizes language needs as a special need, thereby opening up the opportunity for special support in exam contexts (see Deutschmann and Zelime, 2025).
4. The NFC needs to formulate policies related to mixed language approaches and language of support in more detail. Currently, the NFC only deals with this issue in passing: ‘The three national languages can also be used as support languages in the teaching of particular subjects, depending on the context and circumstances of students, teachers and schools, to ensure a maximum level of understanding by all learners’ (Ministry of Education 2013, p.16). Systematic structures and methods for how to provide language support in class are not described at all, which leaves teachers with great uncertainty as to what is expected of them and what level of multilingualism is acceptable in the Seychelles classroom.

In the field – classroom challenges in teaching, learning and examining through English

Teacher-learner communication

Evidence from lesson observations in primary schools in Seychelles (Zelime and Deutschmann, 2018, p.143) shows that classroom communication is dominated by various forms of teacher talk: *Plenary Talk* (Hardman, 2008) – where the teacher does all the talking and learners take notes or copy text from the blackboard; *IRF-talk* (Sinclair and Coulthard, 1975) – initiation-response-feedback talk, where the focus lies on transmission rather than construction of knowledge, and where teachers initiate the exchange, after which learners respond with short answers followed by teacher feedback; and *Safe-Talk* (Hornberger and Chick, 2001) – low-challenge questions and prompts to which learners can respond briefly and sometimes in chorus. A mere 4% of the lesson time we observed was characterized by *Exploratory Talk* – less formal and more dialogic communication where the teacher and students interact to explore new concepts (Barnes, 2008). Results from observations are summarized in Figure 1 below. Other studies from Seychelles corroborate these findings (see Moumou, 2004, for example).

Figure 1: Types of teacher talk observed during lessons of six different primary-school teachers (Zelime, 2024)

Patterns of classroom communication similar to those above have been observed in several classroom studies from L2 MoI contexts in sub-Saharan Africa (Clegg and Afitska, 2011; Brock-Utne and Alidou, 2006; Setati et al., 2002; Bunyi, 2005; Hardman, 2008). Arguably, current language-in-education policies are partly responsible for these teacher-centred pedagogies. There is evidence from the region that teachers resorting to rote learning and lecture-based delivery is partly a consequence of their own limited proficiency and lack of confidence in using the second language effectively (Muller and Nel, 2010; Yasin and Mustafa, 2022). Regardless, these transmission-based models of teaching mean that

learners become passive recipients of information rather than active participants in knowledge making. Complex concepts are rarely negotiated or explored interactively as learners struggle to express themselves and ask questions, further entrenching surface-level understanding. Consequently, opportunities for student-centred learning are significantly reduced, hindering both comprehension and critical thinking development.

Clegg and Afitska (2011, p.61), partly blame the relative absence in teacher training in the region ‘of the specialist pedagogy which learners with low ability in the medium of instruction require’. Without knowledge of targeted pedagogical strategies, such as scaffolding techniques, how to adapt language output to learner proficiencies, and how to apply structured mother-tongue support, teachers are ill equipped to help students. Aspects such as these should be central in teacher training in all subject domains and are crucial for improving educational quality.

Focus on (academic) language proficiency

Assuming a social constructivist learning perspective (Vygotsky, 1978), a general belief that learning takes place in social interaction with others, and that language is an essential part of this process, we need to provide learners with linguistic tools to partake in the learning process. Here, in accordance with Halliday (2004), we recognize three ways of thinking about the relationship between learning and language: learning a language, learning through language, and learning about language. All these aspects should be part of the didactic framework in an L2 MoI context. The concepts of genre and register, as informed by Systemic Functional Linguistics (Halliday and Matthieson, 2014; Polias, 2016) need to be communicated to learners. This would involve explicitly teaching students to recognize and apply different spoken and written genres (descriptions, comparisons, explanations, arguments, for example) and register conventions (formal/informal, everyday/technical, subjective/objective and spoken/written, for example). Learners also need scaffolding and support when reading and writing. For example, teachers can read with students explaining vocabulary and concepts as they progress through the text. Writing can be supported by providing examples and clear templates for different types of texts, and so on.

Language, examination and local context

Another challenge presented by teaching in English is the fact that the language choice risks disconnecting teaching from the local context. Learning materials, for example, are generally produced outside of Seychelles, something which affects teaching as well as examination. In the following example taken from a Key Stage 2 national exam, the illustrative examples are totally foreign to the local context. It is difficult enough to understand the idea of a ‘food web’ when you are nine years old, itself quite a complex metaphor, without the concept being exemplified by animals and plants you are totally unfamiliar with!

25. Study the food web below carefully.

Figure 2: Exam question from the primary 4 national exam 2022

In our own studies (see Zelime and Deutschmann, 2019; Zelime et al., 2018), we have been able to demonstrate how choice of language in examination questions significantly empowered or inhibited learners in expressing their knowledge. Prompted by an image of a local fishing boat and instructed to write about traditional fishing methods, a subject included in the social studies curriculum, learners produced texts in both English and Kreol Seselwa in a counter-balanced design (see Figure 3 below).

The photograph below shows one of the economic activities of Seychelles. Study it carefully and write a short paragraph of about 10 sentences to describe the following:

1. The economic activity it represents.
2. The methods used to catch the fish.
3. The types of fish caught.
4. The benefits of this activity to the community and country.

Figure 3: Task instructions in examination task study
(Zelime et al., 2018)

When asked to write about this image in Kreol Seselwa, learners were able to articulate their local knowledge to a much better degree than when writing in English. Not only were the Kreol Seselwa texts longer, but they also received significantly higher scores when marked by three independent examiners (see Table 1 below).

Table 1: Mean scores in task depending on language

Mean scores (out of 15)	English	Kreol Seselwa	Mean Differences
High stream	7.10	9.07	1.97
Low stream	3.10	5.29	2.19
Girls	6.32	8.40	2.09
Boys	4.38	6.41	2.03
Overall	5.43	7.49	2.06

(Zelime et al., 2018)

Even more striking were the differences in answers to Part 3 of the question, i.e., the descriptions of the types of fishes caught (see Zelime and Deutschmann, 2019, pp.18-20). The 154 Kreol Seselwa texts mentioned 62 unique species, and a total of 908 fish tokens figured in the Kreol text corpus (an average of approximately six species mentioned per text). In contrast, the 154 English texts only contained 27 unique species, many of which were not local fish at all (aquarium fish such as Goldfish and Piranhas, for example). This corpus contained 177 fish tokens (an average of approximately one species mentioned per text). In short, the students were much better equipped linguistically to communicate their knowledge of this question in Kreol Seselwa. This is a clear illustration of Clegg’s concern: ‘If we assess children in a second language it may not tell us what they know’ (Clegg, 2007, p.43). Problems related to decontextualized knowledge become even more acute in secondary school, when the curricula are guided by the international *IGCSE* exams.

The use of Kreol Seselwa as a support language

In our observations, we have failed to find any examples of systematic use of Kreol Seselwa as support language (Deutschmann, 2014; Zelime and Deutschmann, 2018). For example, there were very few instances where Kreol Seselwa was used to explain difficult concepts, and instead it was primarily used to reprimand students. The norm in the classroom seems to be relatively monolingual. For example, in one 45-minute lesson in Primary 4, the phrase ‘in English please’ was heard 28 times (Zelime, 2025).

Policy suggestions

Based on the findings presented above it is clear that language issues present several challenges in the Seychelles classrooms. Arguably, many problems stem from the

pedagogy not being adapted to the needs of second language learners. This in turn leads to learner disengagement and discipline problems, issues increasingly being reported from secondary schools in Seychelles. The following policy suggestions may help address some of these challenges:

1. It is important that all teachers in all subjects be supported to reach proficiency levels in English that allow them to feel totally comfortable to teach through this medium.
2. We recommend a special focus on pedagogy adapted for L2 MoI contexts in teacher training and vocational training of active teachers in all subjects. Such training could include methods aimed at shifting focus from teacher-centred to learner-focused pedagogy and raising awareness of the role of language in this process. For example, teachers need to be made aware of how to increase learners' opportunities to actively contribute to lesson content – by asking open-ended questions, to encourage discussions, to include pair and group work that requires learner engagement etc. Furthermore, teachers need to be trained to adapt their English output to the proficiency levels of the learners – how to use clear and concise language, to use simpler sentence structures, repeating key concepts, how to use examples from the local context to illustrate meaning, how to use body language, images and props to emphasize meaning etc. This type of training is a must for **all** teachers we would argue.
3. There is a need to adapt teaching practices, learning materials and exam content to make them more relevant to the local context. This may also mean making allowances for the use of code switching in exams to enable learners to name local animals, plants, objects and cultural phenomena in Kreol Seselwa. At the very least it is reasonable to make sure that children acquire the English vocabulary to refer to their local contexts.
4. Structured models and guidelines for how to implement language support should be provided to teachers. Here Language Supportive Pedagogy (LSP) has much to offer (see Bowden and Barrett, 2022; Erling et al., 2021). LSP incorporates several language supportive measures. For example, a typical LSP adapted lesson will include structured language supportive measures in the L1 as well as L2 MoI – a preparatory stage where new vocabulary and concepts are explained in the L1, followed by a more formal part of the lesson conducted in the L2, where all tasks are scaffolded to suit the proficiency levels of the learners, and a final debriefing part of the lesson which includes explanations and discussions where learners have an opportunity to solve unclear issues using their L1. Providing structured example models like this would help guide teachers and legitimize the use of Kreol Seselwa in support.

5. Another policy aspect that should be considered is the provision of language support in secondary and primary school contexts where teachers do not speak Kreol Seselwa. This is becoming an increasing problem as the proportion of expatriate teachers is increasing. Here, we would argue for the provision of teacher assistants who are proficient in Kreol Seselwa to help bridge language gaps and support learners. There are also promising indications that such support can partly be provided by AI-tutor apps (see Pejakovic et al., 2025 in this issue).

Language ideologies, identity construction and nation building.

Language-in-education policies have an impact beyond the classroom. The policies set standards for language norms outside the school system and signal the socio-economic 'value' of different languages. In Seychelles, much research has shown that although Kreol Seselwa is important in defining the local creole identity, the value attached to the language in terms of educational and professional opportunities and prestige is very low indeed (see Fleischmann, 2008; Fleischmann, Schwarz and Nick, 2018; Zelime and Deutschmann, 2018). In our studies based on responses from 142 primary school teachers in Seychelles, for example, the vast majority did not believe that a good knowledge of Kreol Seselwa helped in the job market and almost 80% of the teachers felt that Kreol Seselwa should be removed as language of instruction from primary school (Zelime and Deutschmann, 2018, p.139).

In Seychelles society at large, English is strongly favoured as the written medium and, except for the domain of politics, English is also used as the language of formal spoken communication in most professional contexts (see Deutschmann, 2025). Arguably, the preference for written English in local media and other contexts is a direct result of the current language-in-education policies which removes Kreol Seselwa from the curriculum entirely after Primary 6. We have been able to show that this policy greatly contributes to learners' negative attitudes towards writing in Kreol Seselwa in secondary school (Deutschmann and Zelime, 2015).

The policy of merely giving Kreol Seselwa a transitory and supportive role in the education system thus creates negative spiral effects (see Figure 4 below): school does not support full proficiency in higher-level written Kreol Seselwa, leading to a lack of literacy in Kreol Seselwa, leading to a lack of national competence to produce more sophisticated texts in Kreol Seselwa in written media, academia and literature, leading to a lack of use and availability of more complex Kreol Seselwa texts, leading to the status of Kreol Seselwa declining, leading to negative attitudes towards its use in education, leading to a further decline of its role in education, and so on. This type of decline has been going on since the mid-1990s, when policies were changed to reduce the role of Kreol Seselwa as medium of

instruction to the first two years of primary school. The introduction of English as medium of instruction from Primary 1, is arguably another example of this type of effect.

Figure 4: Negative spiral effects of current language policies

The lack of use of Kreol Seselwa in professional and other written contexts in society at large threatens the Ministry of Education’s ambitions towards a ‘quality education system that [...] promotes holistic development, and empowers citizens to participate fully in social and economic development’. The continued dominance of English as the written medium in society at large means that many citizens are disqualified to participate fully in social and economic development. Examples of these social and economic inequities and exclusion include non-access to ongoing debates and discourses in written media such as newspapers, fiction and factual literature; exclusion from professions that require any written input; and the potential to compromise citizens’ legal rights since the judiciary operates entirely in English.

According to Baker (2011, p.72), the negative social effects of excluding local familiar languages from education include ‘less positive self-concept, loss of cultural or ethnic identity, with possible alienation and marginalization’. Despite of this, Kreol Seselwa remains an important definer of the national identity. Seychellois are generally proud of their language, and even in private school contexts, which strongly propagate an English-only policy, parents emphasize the importance of Kreol Seselwa as the ‘mother language’, as the definer of national identity, as something to be proud of, and a given which must be preserved. In the words of one parent: ‘We cannot be born and live in Seychelles and not know how to communicate in creole!’ (Deutschmann, 2024a). Interestingly, in these private school contexts where Kreol Seselwa is totally excluded, most parents want to see it as part of the private school curriculum in the capacity of a ‘home language’ (Deutschmann, 2024b).

Policy suggestions

As discussed above, current language-in-education policies in Seychelles have far-reaching implications, not only in shaping educational outcomes but also by influencing societal norms, identity, and access to opportunities. The current policy, which sidelines Kreol Seselwa after Primary 6, reinforces a cycle of linguistic marginalization that limits the language's development, lowers its perceived value, and restricts its speakers' full participation in society. Nevertheless, Kreol Seselwa is resilient, and is the first language of over 85% of the Seychelles population (National Bureau of Statistics, Seychelles, 2024). Based on the above, we suggest the following future policy considerations.

1. Kreol Seselwa, as first language in the trilingual national policy, merits being a subject throughout the educational system. This could be achieved by the introduction of *Creole Studies* across the curriculum, including at IGCSE level. Such a policy would offer many benefits. It would strengthen students' oral and written skills in their mother tongue, thereby boosting the status of Seselwa. The subject could also cover key areas such as creole linguistics, geography, history (including slavery and colonialism), and cultural expressions like music, art, and literature. A flexible structure could combine core content relevant to other creole contexts with language-specific elements tailored to each nation (see Figure 5. below).

Figure 5: Potential structure of Creole Studies

(from Deutschmann, 2024a, p.65)

2. Given that a new ambitious curriculum for Kreol Seselwa as that suggested above is developed, it is reasonable to make this subject obligatory for all schools in Seychelles, including private schools. Requiring private schools to include local languages in their teaching is a common policy worldwide and a praxis many parents in Seychelles would welcome (see Deutschmann, 2024b).
3. Active efforts to elevate written Kreol Seselwa in society is something which would have many positive effects. This could be achieved by actively sponsoring cultural activities such as literature and drama, sponsoring the publishing of books and

newspapers in Kreol Seselwa, establishing national literary prizes etc. Efforts such as these would help in building a positive national self-image and contribute to the Ministry of Education's vision of 'safeguarding and promoting our unique traditions and cultural values'.

4. Arguably, high levels of spoken and written proficiency in Kreol Seselwa should be a requirement for public service professions in domains such as the police, public health, social services and the criminal justice system. It is reasonable that public servants in Seychelles have these skills when meeting a primarily Kreol-speaking population. A police officer, for example, should be able to produce a verbatim written witness report at a crime scene, and a nurse should be able to explain complex medical procedures to patients in a language they understand. Current language policies whereby Kreol Seselwa ceases to be part of the system after Primary 6, do not prepare learners for such tasks. Introducing language requirements in these professions would automatically result in the elevation of the status of Kreol Seselwa in education to meet these needs.

Summary and ways forward

To promote epistemic equity and improve education in Seychelles, comprehensive language-policy reforms are needed at the policy, school, and societal levels. At the policy level, the English curriculum should better align with the language demands of various subjects, focusing on communicative competence and academic language skills. Introducing 'English for Learning' and fostering collaboration between English and subject teachers, especially for expatriates unfamiliar with Kreol Seselwa, is essential. Tools to identify and support students struggling with English should be developed, with language needs formally recognized as special needs for exam accommodations. The National Curriculum Framework must clarify policies on support languages and mixed language use to guide multilingual classrooms.

In schools, teachers need support to reach high English proficiency and confidence in teaching in English. Teacher training and vocational training should focus on pedagogy for L2 contexts, promoting learner-centered approaches and adapting language use to student proficiency through simplification, visuals, and gestures. Teaching methods, materials, and exams should reflect the local context. Structured models like Language Supportive Pedagogy can guide effective use of both English and Kreol Seselwa. Increasing numbers of expatriate teachers motivates language support via Kreol-speaking assistants or digital tools to ensure all students access the curriculum.

Beyond schools, promoting written Kreol Seselwa in public life through cultural initiatives like publishing, drama, and literary awards can boost national identity and support the

Ministry of Education’s cultural goals. Public service professionals in healthcare, law enforcement, and social work should be proficient in Kreol to ensure effective communication. These changes would elevate Kreol’s status and promote inclusive language practices society wide. Suggestions are summarized in Figure 6. Below.

Figure 6: Suggested language policy reforms to promote inclusive quality education

The work with reforming language-in-education policies is ongoing and we are active in this pursuit. In collaboration with the Ministry of Education, under the framework of the project ‘Understanding understanding’, financed by the Swedish Research Council, we are currently exploring models to bridge the gap between language policies on the intended/stated (textual) level versus the implemented praxis level in the classroom (see Deutschmann and Klymenko, 2023; Deutschmann et al., 2024). This work is not restricted to Seychelles, but pursued in partnership with researchers from Dodoma University, Tanzania; Zanzibar State University; and Bristol University, England. This comparative approach assures a more universal approach that can benefit not only Seychelles, but the entire sub-Saharan region where current language-in-education policies constitute continued hindrances in the pursuit of inclusive quality education.

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